

Title: On breadth and tying: The five stages of conceptual framework G.R.I.E.F

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Abstract: The ultimate aim of any doctoral degree is the generation of new knowledge. The challenge for the novice researcher however is not just explicating an answer to an existing gap in the evidence but explaining the exigency of this elusive within what is established. In order to do this, the social sciences' student scaffolds their study in what is known as the 'conceptual framework'. Yet, as evidenced by the ambiguity the term engenders, the conceptual framework is in itself an enigmatic aspect of doctoral study. Speaking to the challenges of philosophising one's framework and choosing the 'correct' concepts on which to construct it, this article employs the stages of death and dying (Kübler-Ross, 1969) to describe one novice researchers journey towards understanding the nature and function of the metacognitive medium that is the conceptual framework.

Keywords:

Conceptual framework; reflection; mixed methods research; metacognitive insight; researcher development.

Highlights:

- 1: The conceptual framework is an enigmatic aspect of doctoral study.
- 2: If we accept the evolutionary nature of knowledge and the transience of theory, one of the challenges for doctoral students is choosing the 'correct' concepts on which to base their research.
- 3: The conceptual framework is not just a part of the doctoral thesis; it *is* the doctoral thesis.

Introduction:

The nature of knowledge is neither straightforward nor static (Nairn, 2019, Corry et al., 2019) and thus, before researchers can consider the worthiness of their research, they must first frame their work and themselves in relation to what is already done and what is yet to do (Brown, 2010). Forming a bridge between the known and the nascent, the conceptual framework is thus considered a categorical imperative in graduate study (Greene et al., 1989, Hughes et al., 2019). Yet as evidenced by the myriad perspectives the term engenders, the conceptual framework is in itself an enigmatic aspect of doctoral study - further challenging the student to both synthesise salient schemas (Kant, 1781) and to mature their mentation. Certainly, as the interpretive lens through which the research results will be framed and judged, doctoral students must be sure to think about their thinking, and to be cautious in their conceptual choices. Speaking to the challenges of philosophising one's framework and choosing the 'correct' concepts on which to construct it, this article employs the stages of death and dying (Kübler-Ross, 1969) as a reflective, rhetorical, and depictive device to describe my journey towards understanding the nature and function of the metacognitive medium that is the conceptual framework.

On death and dying

Elisabeth Kübler-Ross was a Swiss-American psychiatrist. In her book *On Death and Dying* (Kübler-Ross, 1969) she proposed that incurably ill people experience five stages as they cope with knowing they are dying: denial, anger, bargaining, depression, and acceptance. These stages equally apply, as suggested by Kübler-Ross, to those suffering grief (Kübler-Ross, 1969, Kübler-Ross and Kessler, 2005). Whilst a ground-breaking model at the time, over the years, research has failed to empirically demonstrate the existence of these stages, and the model is now considered to be outdated, inaccurate, and incomplete (Copp, 1998, Kuykendall, 1981, Osterweis et al., 1984). Indeed, Kübler-Ross later acknowledged herself that the stages

were neither linear, unidirectional, or predictable (Kübler-Ross and Kessler, 2005). Criticisms of this model centre not just on the lack of empirical evidence and internal validity (Copp, 1998, Larson, 2013) but also on the fact that the model was a product of a particular culture at a particular time which limited its generalisability (Corr, 2021).

Background:

Antecedent to an explication of my interpretation of the nature and function of the conceptual framework, it is perhaps prudent to provide an insight into my paradigmatic perspectives of ontology, epistemology, and axiology. Taken together, these comprise my worldview (Creswell, 2015, Guba and Lincoln, 1994, Kivunja and Kuyini, 2017) and serve as the intellectual context for the shaping, conduct, and writing of my research (Piantanida and Garman, 2010, Pryor, 2010).

Ontological perspective

Nursing is to promote health, prevent illness, and to care for the sick and dying (Henderson, 1978). It is to advocate, create, educate, influence, and research the health system in which we work (Henderson et al., 1997). Encompassing empirical, ethical, aesthetical, socio-political and personal knowledge (Carper, 1978, White, 1995), the essence of nursing is one of reciprocal and refutational dialecticisms- of practice discipline and academic discipline (Hoeck and Delmar, 2018); of distinct and borrowed bodies of knowledge (Sakamoto, 2018); of experience and education (Benner, 1984); of science and art (Nightingale, 1859); of process and product, and of individuality and interdisciplinarity. Deriving uniqueness from its generality, the reality of nursing is defined in its metaparadigms of person, environment, health and nursing (Fawcett, 1984).

Critically, from ivory tower to swampy lowland (Schön, 1983), the nature of nursing is enduringly established in the human experience- it is done with humans, to humans, for

humans and as humans (Kearns and Mahon, 2021). Thus, nurses live their lives in the intensity of loss, in existential encounters, and in latent and manifest emotion. As nurses are oft the first and only health professional that patients see (All Party Parliamentary Group on Global Health, 2016), it is imperative that the profession and its practitioners ponder how new dimensions of science facilitate new dimensions of artistry (Rogers, 1978, Hoeck and Delmar, 2018). Seen as such, the nature of nursing ontology is intrinsically entwined with and evaluated against the changing shape of society.

Epistemological perspective

My epistemology is strongly linked to my ontology. I believe that as the nature of nursing is one of differentiation and dimensionality, so too must be the knowledge underpinning nursing practice (Sakamoto, 2018, Ou et al., 2017, Bluhm, 2014). Indeed, whilst few would argue against the delivery of patient-centred care based on empirical data (Hoeck and Delmar, 2018), the wealth of knowledge embedded in practice is equally important for a socially situated profession such as nursing (Benner, 1984, Schön, 1983, Gardner et al, 2008). Moreover, the very fact that the nature of knowledge has been subject to interpretation and reinterpretation since the time of Thales of Miletus (O'Grady, n.d) is, I believe, evidence in itself of the fallacy of any one exacting epistemology.

Indeed, while the philosophical incompatibility of competing worldviews will undoubtedly be argued (Holmes et al., 2006, Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2005)- with the positivists assuming the transcendental nature of truth (Hoeck and Delmar, 2018), the post-positivists the primacy of theory (Corry et al., 2019), and the interpretivists the inviolability of individual insight (McNiff and Whitehead, 2001, Kaushik and Walsh, 2019)- it becomes difficult to decide which metaphysical model could be seen as best advancing nursing knowledge or nursing practice when each in their own right are valid (Christensen, 2011, Rycroft-Malone et al., 2004, Schön, 1983). Equally, if all knowledge is provisional (Corry et al., 2019) it follows by

extension that so too are ways of knowing; or as suggested by Chinn and Kramer (1995, p. 4)

“Different ways of knowing are not judged against one another. Rather, different ways of knowing and of creating knowledge are each ... useful for some purpose.”

Thus, to truly consider nursing epistemology it must be situated in nursing ontology. From this viewpoint, apparent epistemic ambivalence can alternatively be established as epistemic eclecticism (Sakamoto, 2018) – a middle ground that accepts the validity of multiple objective and subjective truths. Corry et al. (2019) concur that the current state of play in nursing research methodology is one of pluralism where polyperspectivity affords an opportunity to undertake higher quality and more informed research (Thorne, 2020). A pragmatic epistemology is one such approach that reflects the creative, collaborative, flexible, and holistic ontological nature of nursing while equally recognising that mere method, or establishment of truth are not in themselves an end point; rather, it is the utility of truth which is important (Sakamoto, 2018, Onwuegbuzie and Leech, 2005).

Axiological perspective

As a nurse educator, I believe that if we wish to produce nurses capable of functioning in the human experience, our philosophy and methods must be consistent (Argyris and Schön, 1978). Therefore, I believe my role as a nurse educator is to ensure that the newly registered or postgraduate qualified nurse is more than the mere sum of the parts, but a force for change and a vital resource for health (*Nurses: A Force for Change A Vital Resource for Health*, 2014). I consider my practice as a nurse educator an extension of my practice as a nurse, being that we must treat our students and most junior colleagues with the same compassion, care and commitment that we expect them to exhibit in practice (Department of Health, 2016).

To achieve a nurse capable of practicing at such a level requires more than a didactic approach to teaching and learning. Rather, the approaches required to attain a diverse array of higher-

order outcomes across the taxonomies of educational objectives (Bloom et al, 1956, National Qualifications Authority of Ireland, 2003), Domains of Competence and Principles of Practice (NMBI, 2021, NMBI, 2016) requires a flexible, dynamic, student-centred, and salient methodology. Such an approach is concerned with the potential for human development, regards the student holistically, and accentuates the centrality of the student-teacher dyad.

I therefore reflect my nursing values in educational values that foster choice, collaboration, communication, creativity, and critical thinking - all intrinsically human and pragmatic characteristics. In recognising students' prior knowledge and experience as invaluable teaching and learning tools in the promotion of metacognitive insight (Kruger and Dunning, 1999, Pennycook et al, 2017), my epistemological values are further reflected in pedagogical values that encourage the integration of theoretical, personal, and practical knowledge; a focus on learning how to learn; and the adoption of an autonomous, empowered, self-directed, goal and relevance-orientated approach to learning. Creating a psychologically safe learning space such as this requires the educator to be caring, considerate, patient, and passionate. They must have the ability to motivate, listen, understand, and reflect. They must act with honesty and integrity; and by disregarding certainty as the only acceptable answer, accede that doubt allows for other possibilities. This requires an entrepreneurial mind-set where the trepidation of demonstrating vision, originality, ingenuity, and risk to self-efficacy is offset against the equanimity of improving workplace practices.

Conciliation (Popeian perspective)

Our knowledge of the world is based not just on empirical information, but also on subjective previous experience, our sense impressions, and thought processes (Kant, 1781, Kuhn, 1999). Our knowledge is a product of both *what* and *how* we know- we attain knowledge and truth by comparing one idea with the next and we only come to this through exposure to different stimuli. Certainly, while the epistemology of nursing was epochally established in a dominant

empiricist philosophy (Bender, 2018, Bluhm, 2014, Hoeck and Delmar, 2018) the profession, its patients and its practitioners require more than purely propositional knowledge (Rycroft-Malone et al., 2004, Sikes, 2006). Indeed, just as the nature of nursing knowledge has changed, so too has the nature of nursing ontology. An ageing patient population, local and global healthcare goals (United Nations, 2020), service innovations and the emergence of an ever increasing number of specialist education programmes and advanced roles, amongst others, further drives discussion as to what constitutes the knowledge necessary for contemporary professional practice (Health Information and Quality Authority, 2019, Government of Ireland, 1998, NMBI, 2015, WHO, 2015, 2017, Department of Health, 2019).

While it is important that we recognise epistemic values, equally important are non-epistemic values (Zanotti and Chiffi, 2017, Nairn, 2014, Brinkmann and Kvale, 2005). Values such as creativity, justice, and reflexivity help us think about what we do, why we do it, and how we can improve. They allow us to be more artful in how we apply the science of caring and better define the type of questions worth asking in order to illuminate practical problems and possibilities (Elliott, 1991).

The broad framing of my worldview reflects the evolutionary nature of nursing reality and nursing knowledge (Rogers, 1978), and my personal values within it. It is this integration of theoretical, practical and personal knowledge that defines and develops the nursing profession for the good of itself and of others (Christensen, 2011). Within my worldview, this trinity of theory, philosophy, and practice are all aligned and all are equal (Hoeck and Delmar, 2018). These dissimilar but complimentary components tie together to form a thread through my thesis in a manner, to quote the great English poet, Alexander Pope:

Not *Chaos* -like together crush'd and bruis'd,
But as the World, harmoniously confus'd:
Where Order in Variety we see,
And where, tho' all things differ, all agree.

(Pope, 2014, p. 116)

The five stages of conceptual framework g.r.i.e.f

Just as the lengthy paradigmatic preamble goes some way to describing my approach to my research, it equally goes some way to explain why I reflected on my journey towards understanding the criticality of the conceptual framework. Reflection on and in practice is an integral part of nursing, and an integral part of mixed methods action research- my chosen methodology. Reflection requires practitioners to think about their part in, interpretation of, and meaning attributed to experience by situating it in the context of internal and external sources of knowledge (Mahon and O'Neill, 2020). While there are many magnificent models of reflection, the stages of death and dying was chosen as it perhaps more accurately describes my journey towards understanding. Indeed, while the five stages do in themselves reflect my journey to understanding, conceptually framing this article in the Kübler-Ross model is in itself an exemplum to the utility and fragility of theory- and the challenge of conceptual choice.

Denial.

The 'first' stage of the Kubler-Ross model is denial. Denial! 'I don't really need a conceptual framework!'. And part of this perception comes from the somewhat elusive nature of the conceptual framework. For example, of the 24 doctoral theses from the Institute of Education published between 2016 – 2021 on the DCU repository DORAS, 45% of these do not mention the phrase 'conceptual framework' in their table of contents. One might be forgiven for imagining that if the conceptual framework is such an important aspect of doctoral study, it should be deemed worthy of at least of a notation nod in the initium of the thesis.

But that is not to say that those studies did not have a conceptual frame. As I learnt more about the conceptual framework, I realised that a framework could have been present but not explicit in the skeletal structure of the thesis; or perhaps it was not required by the chosen methodology (such as grounded theory). Indeed, authors such as Kivunja (2018) suggest that

while you need to design and explain your theoretical framework, you are not required to explicitly discuss the conceptual. Accepting an initial position that the conceptual framework is required- either tacitly or explicitly, I moved to next stage.

Anger

Anger- that the terms conceptual and theoretical framework get conflated in the literature which makes it hard to know whether to use none, one or both; or indeed what the phrase actually means! For example, authors such as Fain (2004), Parahoo (2006), Polit and Beck (2012), and Imenda (2017) suggest that ‘theoretical framework’ should be used when research is underpinned by theory and that a ‘conceptual framework’ should be used when drawing on multiple concepts. Berman (2013) suggests that conceptual frameworks have grown from the theoretical framework to reflect the process of personal conceptualisation and the need for multiple theoretical frameworks in doctoral studies. Conversely, Hughes et al. (2019) infer that both are needed by suggesting that the conceptual framework builds upon the theoretical. But Hughes et al. (2019) also state that the conceptual framework is only necessary in qualitative research when pursuing either a new or an underdeveloped area, suggesting that it is not needed at all in some instances.

Further confusion arises when one considers the function of the conceptual framework within a given approach to the research. The logic of inductive research is different to that of deductive, meaning theoretical and conceptual frameworks play different roles in each (Parahoo, 2006, Varpio et al., 2020, Hughes et al., 2019), which begs the question as to what the mixed methods researcher (like me) is expected to do! It is indeed ironic that a term intended to situate and elucidate research is so poorly defined, and so poorly understood. However, as every research student knows, at some stage you come across that one reading that makes sense to you. For me, that was the definition proposed by Kivunja (2018, p. 47) that the conceptual framework:

is the total, logical orientation and associations of anything and everything that forms the underlying thinking, structures, plans, practices, and implementation of your entire research project. [It] comprises your thoughts on identification of the research topic, the problem to be investigated, the questions to be asked, the literature to be reviewed, the theories to be applied, the methodology you will use, the methods, procedures and instruments, the data analysis and interpretation of findings, recommendations, and conclusions you will make.

If we accept this definition it means that the conceptual framework is comprised of, gives structure to, resonates with, and forms a bridge between, all aspects of the research process across the continuum of conception to conclusion (Parahoo, 2006, Leshem and Trafford, 2007, Berman, 2013, Adom et al., 2018, Hughes et al., 2019, Imenda, 2017). Axiomatically, it is a metacognitive, operational, and philosophical element of the entire research process (Kivunja, 2018) covering the *breadth* of the thesis and *tying* it together. Therefore, despite the assertions of Adom et al. (2018) that the conceptual framework is normally or naturally placed within the literature review chapter; it is my assertion that the conceptual framework cannot be condensed to a neat chapter within my thesis. Rather, in one sense, the conceptual framework *is* the thesis (Table 1).

Table 1: Overview of constitutive elements of my conceptual framework (based on questions posed by Kivunja 2018)

Question to consider when developing a conceptual framework	Chapters and subchapters in the thesis where the answer is found
1. What do you want to do in your research?	Introduction, background, problem statement, purpose statement, research questions, methodology aims.
2.1 Why do you want to do it?	Significance, worldview.
2.2 Why is it important to conduct that research?	Introduction, significance, worldview, literature review.
2.3 Which specific objectives will it pursue?	Aims, purpose statement, research questions, methods.
2.4 How much scope will it cover?	Operational definitions, research questions, population and sampling, data collection tools.
3.1 Why it is significant?	Introduction, background, literature review.
3.2 What aims will it seek to achieve?	Significance, aims.
4.1 How do you plan to do it?	Methodology, methods, ethical considerations, data protection impact assessment.
4.2 Which methodology will you apply?	Methodology, pragmatism, action research, mixed methods research, educational entrepreneurial approach (Crotty, 2014) to action research.
4.3 Which methods will you use?	Methods, data collection tools, data collection techniques.
4.4 Who will be your participants?	Operational definitions, population, and sampling.
4.5 How will you gather data?	Literature review, data collection techniques, data management plan.
4.6 How will you analyse the data?	Methods, results, data integration.
5.1 How will you make meaning of the data?	Worldview, literature review, theoretical framework; data analysis, results, recommendations, limitations, conclusions.

5.2 What theoretical framework will you use?	Literature review, theoretical framework.
5.3 Which software will you use?	Data analysis tools.
5.4 Which skills will you need?	Methods, data analysis tools, data analysis techniques.
6. Which worldview will you locate your research in?	Worldview, positioning, pragmatism, mixed methods research, action research, educational entrepreneurial approach (Crotty, 2014) to action research.
7.1 How will you report your findings?	Results, recommendations, conclusions, conceptual framework, appendix (if presented at conferences, published etc).
<i>Note: each major chapter within the thesis has a section summarising the contribution of that chapter to the overall conceptual framework.</i>	

Bargaining

Having come to an understanding of the function of the conceptual framework one might next arrive at the bargaining stage. You decide that if you must include one you will- and the best thing is just to get it done. However, this is a short-lived stage quickly leading to the next.

Depression

Depression – the realisation that you do not just do one conceptual framework, you do many. As suggested by Miles and Huberman (1994) and Chowdhury (2019), conceptual frameworks are iterative- they are simply the current version of the researchers map of the territory being investigated. They change as the research progresses and therefore, they are not written once, they are written many times. In fact, Hughes et al. (2019) suggest that it is not unusual for doctoral students to present before and after conceptual frameworks to show important contrasts from dissertation proposal to the final dissertation.

Acceptance

When I reflect on my coming to an understanding, I realise and accept that it is only when the framework is truly conceptualised that one can possibly realise the value of it. The challenge for us doctoral students is if we accept that the conceptual framework is the thesis, then that can only happen as we conclude our doctoral journey. For me, that point is at least a few years from now.

But as an iterative process, and as I currently understand it, there are many things I have learnt by reflecting on the nature and function of the conceptual framework. As evidenced by the many refutational positions in the literature, trying to arrive at an understanding can cause you grief in that it is challenging and troublesome. But as a maturation process for both the research and the researcher (Leshem and Trafford, 2007), when one does arrive at an understanding, it can lead to an exclamation of surprise- ‘Good grief!’ And this G.R.I.E.F forms a five-stage acronym that explains my interpretation of the nature and function of the conceptual framework in doctoral study:

- G: The conceptual framework is a global element of the thesis; it is generative and frames your goals.
- R: It is rational, refining, and reflective of the researcher, the researched and the readings (Leshem and Trafford, 2007, Chowdhury, 2019). It adds relevance and resolves the connection between theory and practice (Lewin, 1951).
- I: It is iterative, illuminating, and idiosyncratic...
- E: Elucidative, evolving, and exculpatory.
- F: It is fluid and gives focus, but importantly, it helps you finish what you set out to achieve!

Conclusion

The ultimate aim of any doctoral degree is the generation of new knowledge. But what is knowledge? Knowledge is something we come to by comparing and contrasting one idea with the next, and we only come to this through exposure to, and critically reflecting on, different stimuli (Mahon and O'Neill, 2020). Just as the conceptual framework is simply the researcher's current translation of the territory to be investigated, this article reflects my current understanding of the conceptual framework. Whether that understanding is right or wrong I cannot possibly know now (Kruger and Dunning, 1999), but I do know my understanding will develop and evolve as I as a researcher develop and evolve. Indeed, as seekers of truth, it is right that we look within as well as without as we travel our journey toward attaining a doctoral degree. As philosophers, it is right that we practice our theory and theorise our practice to ensure that we produce personal, as well as professional knowledge.

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